

The Quaternary Ammonium Iodides of Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine.

BY M. Q. DOJA.

Thomsen (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1586) first obtained the methyl iodide of dimethyl-*p*-toluidine by the repeated treatment of *p*-toluidine with methyl iodide (*cf.* Hübner, Tolle and Athenstadt, *Annalen*, 1884, 224, 337; Wedekind, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 773; Von Braun, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2137). Any other alkyl iodide of dimethyl-*p*-toluidine has not been described so far. The effect of the systematic addition of alkyl iodides to dimethyl-*p*-toluidine has now been studied and it has been found that the alkyl iodides of dimethyl-*p*-toluidine possess a great tendency towards the formation of syrups (*cf.* Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 1406; Ullmann, *Annalen*, 1903, 327, 111), as found earlier in the case of dimethylaniline by Wedekind (*Annalen*, 1901, 318, 90; *cf.* Menschutkin, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, 6, 41; Winkler and Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1147).

The yield of the quaternary iodides of dimethyl-*p*-toluidine together with the corresponding values for dimethylaniline are given below.

Alkyl iodide,	Yield with dimethylaniline.	Yield with dimethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine.
Methyl iodide	88.9%	93.8%
Ethyl iodide	16.2	27.7
Propyl iodide	28.1	40.0
Butyl iodide	17.0	32.0
Amyl iodide	38.7	42.0

It will be seen that there is an alternate decrease and increase with rise in the series. There is a sharp drop in the yield from the methyl iodide to the ethyl iodide, then the differences become less pronounced as we ascend the homologous series. It will also be noted that the yield of the quaternary ammonium iodide of dimethyl-*p*-toluidine is in every case greater than the corresponding compound of dimethylaniline, an observation quite in conformity with the modern conception of electronics.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The reactants in each of the experiments described below were mixed together in a 50 c.c. flask provided with a condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube.

The quaternary iodides are all soluble in water, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and chloroform but insoluble in ether, benzene, toluene, xylene and hexane. In the last liquid they turn yellow in the cold and brown on boiling. Unless otherwise stated the quaternary iodides were all recrystallised from absolute alcohol with a little animal charcoal forming colourless crystals.

The melting points recorded were all determined in Mason's electrical melting point apparatus in sealed tubes and the action of heat was also studied in a test tube (0.3" x 3.0") in a glycerine bath.

Trimethyl-p-tolylammonium Iodide.—Methyl iodide (2.0 g.) and dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (1.75 g.) were each dissolved in 10 c. c. of ether, well mixed, allowed to stand for 24 hours and then heated on the water-bath for 9 hours. After cooling the separated solid was filtered at the pump and washed with ether, yield 3.52 g.

From dilute solutions in absolute alcohol the substance slowly crystallises in colourless transparent bipyramids (*cf.* Wedekind, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 517). It is not hygroscopic in the pure state (*cf.* Vorländer and Siebert, *Ber.*, 1919, 52, 304). A mixture with ether turns gradually yellow when exposed to air and diffused light (*cf.* Datta and Ghosh, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 1021.) It sublimes unchanged at 206-210° and melts at 202°. (Found: N, 5.21, 5.17, 5.11; I, 45.83, 45.76; C₁₀H₁₈NI requires N, 5.05; I, 45.85 per cent).

Dimethyl-p-tolyethylammonium Iodide.—Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (3 g.) and ethyl iodide (3.5 g.) were each dissolved in 20 c.c. of benzene, mixed together and heated for 18 hours on a water-bath. On cooling a solid separated which was filtered, washed with benzene (5 c.c.), and quickly placed in a vacuum desiccator. After continuous evacuation for 8 hours the solid was left in the desiccator for 4 days. The dry solid was dissolved in cold absolute alcohol and ether added until a precipitate was just obtained. The mixture was placed in a frigidaire and the addition of ether continued twice a day until no further precipitation took place. The separated solid was filtered,

washed with a mixture of ether and alcohol (10:1), and dried (1.8 g.). It was recrystallised from absolute methyl alcohol (charcoal) as transparent bipyramids, m. p. 196°. It dissolves with difficulty in cold acetone but easily on boiling. It is soluble with great difficulty in carbon disulphide even on boiling. It turns brownish on the surface at 107-110° and sublimes with partial decomposition at 208-11°. (Found: N, 5.02, 4.95, 4.88; I, 43.28, 43.36, 43.29. $C_{11}H_{18}NI$ requires N, 4.81; I, 43.64 per cent).

Dimethyl-p-tolyl-n-propylammonium Iodide.—Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (2 g.) and *n*-propyl iodide (2.5 g.) were heated on the steam-bath for 22 hours. On keeping for 2 weeks crystals embedded in a thick reddish brown syrup were obtained. The mass was dissolved in absolute alcohol and ether added to the solution placed in the frigidaire till no further precipitation occurred. The supernatant liquid was poured off and the solid pressed on a porous plate and dried, m. p. 200°, yield 1.8 g. When heated in a test tube it begins to melt at 197° and the liquid sublimes with slight decomposition at 199°. (Found: N, 4.56, 4.66, 4.71; I, 41.29, 41.25, 41.37. $C_{12}H_{20}NI$ requires N, 4.59; I, 41.64 per cent).

Dimethyl-p-tolyl-n-butylammonium Iodide.—Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (1.5 g.) and *n*-butyl iodide (2 g.) were heated for 16 hours on a steam-bath. On keeping for a fortnight, the slightly syrupy crystalline mass was dissolved in absolute alcohol and ether slowly added until a precipitate was just formed. It was then placed in the frigidaire and 10 c.c. of ether gradually added every day until no more precipitation took place. The precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with ether and dried (1.12 g.). The compound is obtained as a compact mass of transparent laminæ, m.p. 201-2°. It is insoluble in ligroin but rapidly turns brownish yellow in the cold and reddish brown on heating. When heated in a test tube it sublimes unchanged at 198-205°. (Found: N, 4.43, 4.58, 4.50; I, 39.86, 39.73, 39.77. $C_{13}H_{22}NI$ requires N, 4.38; I, 39.81 per cent).

Dimethyl-p-tolyl-n-amylammonium Iodide.—Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (2 g.) and *n*-amyl iodide (3 g.) were mixed together and left for 24 hours. The solution was then gently heated in a Babo's bath for 25 minutes, and the white solid thus produced allowed to stand for a couple of days. The compound was dissolved in warm absolute alcohol, the solution cooled and ether added until no further precipitation took place. The solid was filtered, washed with a mixture of ether and alcohol (20:1) and dried (2.10 g.). It was recrystallised from benzene-

alcohol (1:1) with a little animal charcoal as microscopic crystals, m. p. 199-201°. When heated in a test tube it turns brownish on the surface in some places at 106°, which colour disappears at 162° and then sublimes with slight decomposition at 192-97°. (Found: N, 4'31, 4'53, 4'42; I, 37'88, 38'43, 38'37. $C_{14}H_{24}NI$ requires N, 4'20; I, 38'14 per cent).

Dimethyl-p-tolylallylammonium Iodide. — Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (2 g.) and allyl iodide (2.5 g.) were mixed together, when after a few minutes a vigorous reaction ensued and the reaction mixture began to boil. The mixture was cooled and then allowed to stand for 24 hours. It was then heated on a boiling water-bath for 5 hours. After keeping for 3 weeks the thick syrup was dissolved in absolute alcohol (35 c.c.), placed in the frigidaire and treated with ether (40 c.c.) and 300 c.c. of ether was dropped into the solution placed in the frigidaire and the solution left for 4 days in the frigidaire. Rosettes of crystals mixed with a thick reddish brown syrup separated out. The ether was poured off and the crystals dried on a porous plate, when yellowish flattened needles (0.93 g.) were obtained, m. p. 197°. When heated in a test tube it turns yellowish at 102°-108° and sublimes with slight decomposition at 193-98°. (Found: N, 4'69, 4'67, 4'86; I, 42'11; 41'78, 41'83. $C_{12}H_{18}NI$ requires N, 4'62; I, 41'91 per cent).

Dimethyl-phenyl-n-amylammonium Iodide. — Dimethylaniline (3 g.) and *n*-amyl iodide (5 g.) were mixed together and after 1 hour the mixture was gently heated on a sand-bath for 15 minutes. The solid produced after a vigorous reaction was left for 24 hours, dissolved in cold absolute alcohol (180 c.c.) and then treated with ether (270 c.c.). The mixture was allowed to stand for 10 minutes, the separated solid filtered, washed with 10 c.c. of ether and dried (3.1 g). It is obtained as glistening mica-like thin flakes, m.p. 205°. It dissolves with difficulty in hot acetone giving a light yellow solution. It does not dissolve in ligroin but turns yellow first and then brown. When heated in a test tube it sublimes gradually unchanged at 204-218°. (Found: N, 4'42, 4.44, 4'57; I, 39'78, 39'83. $C_{13}H_{22}NI$ requires N, 4'38; I, 39'81 per cent).